

Once again September appears to be the start of a very busy and productive time for the DDI Alliance. This issue provides information about many DDI-related events and activities taking place in coming months. Looking ahead to 2013, we will mark the 10-year anniversary of the DDI Alliance, and 2003 was also the year that DDI 2 was published. There is much to celebrate and much work still to be done!

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

DDI Alliance Revises Organizational Documents

At its most recent meeting in June in Washington, DC, the DDI Alliance prepared for changes to its foundational and organizational documents. The External Review report of 2011 recommended changes to the Alliance Bylaws, and a Governance Task Force was established to work on that document and the related membership form.

The documents are currently under review and should be made available early in 2013. Also being reviewed are the document describing how the DDI specifications are changed and updated, and the organization's Charter, Mission, and Guiding Principles.

The revised Bylaws will also lead the way toward new elections for

the Executive Board of the Alliance (former Steering Committee) as well as the Chair and Vice Chair of that body. Although the terms of Chair Chuck Humphrey, University

of Alberta, and Mari Kleemola, Finnish Social Science Data Service, technically expire in January 2013, they have agreed to remain in their roles until new elections take place.

The Expert Committee of the DDI Alliance met on June 4, 2012, in Washington, DC, in connection with the annual IASSIST conference. From left, Ron Nakao, Stanford University; Anita Rocha, University of Washington; Tom Piazza, University of California, Berkeley; Jonathan Palmer, Australian Bureau of Statistics; Joachim Wackerow, GESIS.

New Members Join Alliance

The DDI Alliance is pleased to welcome two new members:

- Eurostat (Contact: Adam Wronski; Expert Committee Representative: Marco Pellegrino)
- DIPF ~ German Institute for International Educational Research (Contact and Expert Committee Representative: Ingo Barkow)

Plans for NADDI in 2013 Shaping Up

Plans for the first ever [North America DDI Users Conference](#), to take place April 2-3, 2013, at the University of Kansas, are taking shape. The conference will be held in the [Kansas Union](#), and the conference hotel is the [Oread Hotel](#).

An important focus of the conference will be the use of DDI by individual research teams throughout the data life cycle. There will be two days of presentations and a training session after the conference. Conference planning volunteers are welcomed.

DDI Training Held in Luxembourg

Arofan Gregory, Open Data Foundation, and Wendy Thomas, Minnesota Population Center, provided training in DDI to members of the Eurostat community on September 5 and 6 in Luxembourg. Eurostat recently joined the Alliance, and this meeting served as an introduction for Eurostat to the Alliance and the DDI specification. Discussions focused on using DDI in statistical agencies, how DDI fits with other standards like the GSBPM and GSIM, and how best to leverage DDI in the European Statistical System.

EDDI 2012 to Feature DDI Tools Competition

The Fourth Annual European User Conference will take place in Bergen, Norway, on December 3-4, 2012, hosted by the Norwegian Social Science Data Service (NSD). Svein Nordbotten, professor emeritus (information science) at the University of Bergen and head of the research enterprise Svein Nordbotten & Associates, will give the Keynote Address.

The conference organizers invite developers and practitioners to participate in the first DDI Tools Competition to show the world what can be done for visualizing the content of DDI instances.

DDI Expert Committee Chair Chuck Humphrey and Vice Chair Mari Kleemola (right), shown with Director Mary Vardigan, have agreed to stay on as a Transition Team until the Alliance holds new elections in mid-2013.

The main goal of the DDI Tools Competition is to develop and showcase innovative applications that present DDI-based information to the end-user.

Conceivable examples are (but are not limited to): generators for smart codebooks in the form of PDF or Microsoft Help files, parts of Web information systems or portals, and stand-alone applications. The tools should be able to consume DDI Lifecycle (3.1) instances, and should be made available as Free Software (i.e., source code as Open Source). Further details on the competition and on sample instances will be announced on October 8. The deadline for submissions of the final program code is November 17, 2012.

EDDI 2012 is organized jointly by [NSD - Norwegian Social Science Data Services](#), [GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences](#), and [IDSC of IZA - International Data Service Center of the Institute for the Study of Labor](#).

The deadline for paper submissions is October 3. If you are interested in presenting a paper, please use the [online submission system](#) of the

conference. This system may also be used to submit an abstract for tools.

For more information about the conference, see the conference Web site at: <http://www.eddi-conferences.eu/eddi12>.

DDI Training for Data Librarians Offered

A two-day workshop for data librarians and archivists entitled “[Data Documentation Initiative \(DDI\) for the Data Librarian](#)” will take place November 12–13, 2012, at the Perry-Castañeda Library, University of Texas at Austin.

Taught by Wendy Thomas, the workshop will focus on the use of DDI-Lifecycle by data librarians and archivists as a means of managing data deposited to their systems and supporting the use of DDI by their research community. The first day of the workshop will provide information in a lecture format providing an overview of the DDI model and its applications and identify specific structures within DDI that support data management, data discovery, data processing and study development. The second day will provide hands-on work

with creating DDI content from the perspective of the librarian/archivist and from the perspective of the researcher.

Colectica Releases Open Source Metadata Converter

Colectica has released an Open Source metadata converter project. The first converter is a Blaise to DDI 3 converter. The Metadata Converters may be used under the terms of the Lesser GNU Public License (LGPL).

Funding for the Blaise to DDI research project was provided in part by a grant from the U.S. National Institute on Aging. Funding for enhancements and the open source publication of the project was provided by the Canadian Foundation for Innovation through the Canadian Research Data Centre Network (CRDCN) Metadata Project.

Project: <http://www.colectica.com/open-source/>

Source: <https://github.com/Colectica/MetadataConverters/>

Open Metadata Portal Launched

IASSIST 2012 marked the launch of OpenMetadata.org (OM), a new Web portal, supported and operated by Metadata Technology and its partner Integrated Data Management Services (IDMS). The portal aims to provide online access to standards-based data/metadata services and to development tools and libraries for the management of statistical data. The initial release of the OpenMetadata.org portal includes:

- A DDI-based catalog of surveys driven by metadata harvested from public repositories around the globe, providing access to information for thousands of surveys and millions of variables.
- OMAD: an interactive directory of statistical agencies containing profile information for hundreds of organizations involved in the production, management, and access of official statistics. The agency directory service goes beyond the simple address book concept and facilitates the discovery of and access to standards-based online data services.

Dagstuhl Workshops to Take Place in October

Two advanced workshops relating to DDI will be held at Schloss Dagstuhl, Leibniz Center for Informatics, in Wadern, Germany, in 2012.

The first, organized by GESIS-Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, will be a workshop on “Semantic Statistics for Social, Behavioural, and Economic Sciences: Leveraging the DDI Model for the Web,”

to be held October 15-19. This is a follow-up to the workshop held on this topic in 2011.

The second workshop, “DDI Lifecycle: Moving Forward,” a workshop to create a UML model for the DDI specification and expand its coverage, will be held October 22-26. It is being organized by representatives from GESIS, Open Data Foundation, Minnesota Population Center, and the DDI Alliance.

USING RDF TO DESCRIBE AND LINK SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA TO RELATED RESOURCES ON THE WEB

By Stefan Kramer, Amber Leahey, Humphrey Southall, Johanna Vompras, and Joadim Wackerow

2012-08-10

DDI Working Paper Series – Semantic Web, No. 1

This paper is part of a series that focuses on DDI usage and how the metadata specification should be applied in a variety of settings by a variety of organizations and individuals. Support for this working paper series was provided by the authors' home institutions; by GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences; by Schloss Dagstuhl - Leibniz Center for Informatics; and by the DDI Alliance.

A new DDI paper resulting from the Dagstuhl Semantic Statistics workshop in 2011 is now available. The photo on the cover page shows the sculpture of a lion in the garden of Schloss Dagstuhl.